

ESTABLISHMENT AND MAINTENANCE OF CENTRALIZED SERVICE AGENCIES
IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Mirzaeva Shirin Nodirovna

Assistant-teacher of the Department "Real economy"
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service
E-mail: mirzayeva.shirin.nodirovna@gmail.com
Telephone number: +998905020271

Abstract: This article discusses issues such as the criteria for the activities of business structures in the service sector and the business environment. In particular, the author's views on improving the efficiency of business structures in the service sector, the development of domestic and foreign economists in the service sector, the criteria for evaluating their activities and the author's views on this topic are reflected.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, business, small business, economy, service, business environment, private property, competition, entre.

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Abstract: В данной статье рассматриваются такие вопросы, как критерии деятельности бизнес-структур в сфере услуг и деловой среды. В частности, отражены взгляды автора на повышение эффективности предпринимательских структур в сфере услуг, разработки отечественных и зарубежных экономистов в сфере услуг, критерии оценки их деятельности и взгляды автора на данную тему.

Keywords: предпринимательство, бизнес, малый бизнес, экономика, сервис, бизнес-среда, частная собственность, конкуренция, предприниматель..

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Abstract: Respublikamizda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida shakllangan tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmni tashkil etish va xizmatlar bozorini to'liq nazorat qilish va boshqarish. Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida iqtisodiy samaradorlikni belgilovchi ko'rsatkichlarni tasniflash va mehnat samaradorligini baholash metodologiyasini o'rganish..

Keywords: tadbirkorlik, biznes, kichik biznes, iqtisodiyot, xizmat ko'rsatish, ishbilamonlik muhiti, xususiy mulk, raqobat, tadbirkor.

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Enter.

In the context of economic liberalization, the modernization of the national economy and its integration into the world economy depends in many respects on a correct and reasonable investment policy.

Development of investment activity in our country in accordance with the conditions of the economic environment, ensuring their activity in all spheres of economic life of society, modernization of the national production process and ensuring sustainable economic growth is one of the important factors. Therefore, one of the main issues on the agenda of the reforms carried out by our government every year is to attract investment to the national economy.

Areas of organization and financing of investments in market conditions A number of measures and investment programs and projects are being developed for the development of production of enterprises stabilizing the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At present, the organization and financing of investments are carried out in the following areas of investment policy:

- pursuing a policy with a clear goal of further liberalization of foreign economic activity, the introduction of a system of some incentives for the use of their income for foreign investment in the export of goods;
- Further improvement of legal, social and economic conditions for attracting foreign investment, mainly capital sources in the economy of the Republic;
- Carrying out an open door policy towards foreign investment, which will help Uzbekistan to develop a system of economy that brings world-class technology.

The creation of perfect legislation in all countries of the world, ensuring its unconditional implementation, raising the legal culture of the population and officials, clearly defining the rights and responsibilities of citizens, public authorities and administration are important areas. In this process, the legal services of government agencies and organizations, businesses play an important role. Legal service from the process of preparation of draft normative legal acts, legal examination, acceptance to ensuring their implementation; conclusion, amendment, termination and execution of economic contracts; providing legal means of property protection; compliance with labor legislation and strengthening labor discipline; protection of the rights and legitimate interests of relevant bodies and business entities in courts and other organizations; actively participates in legal education.

Because in improving market relations, further liberalizing the economy, the development of business structures, as a result of which the country's budget is stable, gross domestic product (GDP), employment is being addressed.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

As a result of the creation of certain conditions for the development of this sector, the establishment of benefits for taxes, customs and other payments, the effective use of bank loans in a short period of time, the number of business entities is growing. According to official data, in 2019 it reached 59.3%. However, this figure was 1.5% in the early years of independence and 31.0% in 2000. However, there are some problems in this regard. The main reason for this is the activity of business structures the lack of an economic mechanism to meet today's demand, they use of economic means in the activity, other business economic relations with entities and public authorities is that their relationship is imperfect. At the same

time, the issues related to improving the efficiency of business entities in the service sector, in particular, the ways to identify and analyze the system of indicators that represent them, are still unresolved, which indicates the urgency of the topic of this study.

There are a number of scientific works of domestic and foreign economists on the development of business structures in the field of services, the criteria for evaluating their activities. Theoretical foundations of small business and private entrepreneurship and social significance A.Smith, J.B.Sey, Dj.M.Keins, I.Shumpeter, A.V.Chayanov, K.A.Raitskiy, I.A.Juravleva {1}, A.P.Kiselev {2 } studied by economists such as. They have contributed to the development of the theory of small business and private entrepreneurship.

This topic has been discussed by Uzbek scientists during the years of independence A number of scientific studies have been conducted on In particular, S.S. Gulomov {3},

G'.X.Kudratov {4}, Yo.Abdullaev {5}, M.S.Kosimova {6}, B.Xodiev {7}, A.Abdullaev {8}, D.Suyunov {9}, M.K. .Pardaev {10}, S.K.Salaev {11}, B.A.Abdukarimov {12}, G.S.Sevlikyants and E.N.Khodjaevs {13}, B.B. The research of Mardonov and AM Saidov {14} in this regard should be noted.

Today, the processes of economic reform and modernization in the socio-economic life of the republic are aimed at ensuring the further development of the service sector. The share of this sector in GDP, the number of people employed in the economy, taxes paid to the state budget, the creation of new jobs, filling the domestic market with consumer goods is growing rapidly, and a legal framework has been created to continue this process.

Therefore, in our study, the service sector is devoted to the study of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the system of management of the competitiveness of business structures.

For this purpose, the following issues will be considered:

- Criteria for the activities of business structures in the field of services and the work environment;

- Functions and features of small business in the field of services;

- Introduction of an institutional environment and innovations based on effective business structures - as important conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The formation and prospects of the management system of competitiveness of business structures in the Republic of Uzbekistan are very important for the development of society and, therefore, the most relevant and justified is one of the primary problems that attracts the attention of researchers.

Research methodology.

In order to clarify the criteria for the activities of business structures in the service sector and the content of the business environment, we found it necessary to follow a certain logical sequence: first, the essence of entrepreneurship and business concepts are scientifically explained, then the current legislation reveals the characteristics of existing business structures; Theoretical interpretation of the activities of business structures in the field and the concept of the process of their management based on the rules of economic systematization commentary is given on the socio-economic content of the service sector the author's new approach is substantiated. On April 17, 2018 on the basis of the Presidential Decree No. 1957 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of services in rural areas in 2018-2021" on April 17, 2018, the Governor's Resolution No. 92-K was adopted. Also, the "Program for the accelerated development of services in rural areas in Andijan region in 2018-2021" was developed the fact that it has been confirmed is a proof of our opinion above.

As a result, the share of the services sector in the country's GDP reached 52% in 2018 and 53% in 2019, which is evidence of the positive trends in the economy. However, today in developed countries this figure is 60-70 percent of GDP. This means that the service sector in our country needs to develop faster than other sectors.

Summary.

For this reason, business structures in the Republic of Uzbekistan today formation and prospects of the competitiveness management system

The need for targeted research is high. Therefore, in our study, the service sector is business structures to study the theoretical and methodological bases of the competitiveness management system is dedicated.

For this purpose, the following issues will be considered:

- Criteria for the activities of business structures in the field of services and the work environment;
- Functions and features of small business in the field of services;
- institutional environment based on effective business structures and introduction of innovations - entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan as important conditions of development.

Competitiveness of business structures in the Republic of Uzbekistan the formation and prospects of the management system are crucial to the development of society important and therefore the most up-to-date and justifiable of economics the first level that attracts the attention of researchers is one of the problems.

Criteria for the activities of business structures in the field of services and a certain logic in research to illuminate the content of the business environment we

found it necessary to follow a sequence: initially entrepreneurial activity and business.

The essence of the concepts is explained scientifically, then within the framework of applicable law revealing the features of the existing business structures in our country and finally business structures in the service sector based on the theoretical interpretation of its activities and the rules of economic systematization.

The scientific and methodological of the necessary elements of the concept of the process of their management commentary is given on the socio-economic content of the service sector the author's new approach is substantiated.

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